

Explore how AI is applied in hematology.

Join four practical sessions this May.

The **SYNTHEMA** project, in collaboration with **ERN-EuroBloodNet**, invites you to take part in a focused webinar series on artificial intelligence in hematology.

This training programme offers a clear introduction to how **AI** is shaping research and care in **rare hematological diseases**. It explains how synthetic data generation and federated learning can address data scarcity while supporting secure, cross-border collaboration.

Through real clinical use cases such as Acute Myeloid Leukemia and Sickle Cell Anaemia, participants will see how these approaches can support diagnosis, research, and patient outcomes.

[Register now](#)

Who is it for?

Patients, healthcare professionals, and patient organisations.

What to expect

Across four sessions in May, the programme will cover:

- **8 May:** SYNTHEMA infrastructure for synthetic data generation
- **15 May:** Regulatory and ethical frameworks, including the EU AI Act
- **22 May:** Data standardisation, interoperability, and anonymisation methods
- **29 May:** Applications in rare hematological diseases

Each session runs from 12:30 to 14:00 CEST. You can attend the full programme or join individual sessions, depending on your interests.

Why attend?

You will gain a practical understanding of how AI can be applied in hematology today, including tools and approaches that support secure data use and

international research collaboration.

Secure your place!

[Register now](#)

SYNTHEMA is an initiative funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101095530

This email was sent to {{contact.EMAIL}}
You've received this email because you've subscribed to our newsletter.

[Unsubscribe](#)

